

SELF-REPAIRING FLIGHT CONTROL SYSTEM PROGRAM OVERVIEW

Capt Robert A. Eslinger
AFWAL/FIGL
Wright-Patterson AFB Ohio 45433-6553

Phillip R. Chandler
AFWAL/FIGX
Wright-Patterson AFB Ohio 45433-6553

Abstract

The Air Force Flight Dynamics Laboratory initiated the Self-Repairing Flight Control System Program in 1984. The program objective is to significantly improve the reliability, maintainability, survivability, and life cycle cost of aircraft flight control systems through aerodynamic reconfiguration and maintenance diagnostics. When a control surface becomes impaired due to a failure or battle damage, a reconfiguration strategy uses the remaining control surfaces to substitute for the lost force and moment generating capability. The reduced criticality of individual control surfaces allows for simplification of upstream flight control system components, e.g., actuators. Reconfiguration technology includes a Positive Pilot Alert system which informs the pilot of impairments and new performance limits. Maintenance diagnostics technology includes both expert ground based systems, to help flight line maintenance personnel, and airborne systems, to begin the diagnostics process before the aircraft lands. The diagnostics systems significantly decrease the time to diagnose failures and lower cannot duplicate and retest OK maintenance actions. The program transitions technology to current and advanced fighter aircraft through feasibility studies, development studies, design criteria development, ground simulations, field demonstrations, and fighter flight tests.

1. Background

The Air Force has placed major emphasis on reliability and maintainability (R&M) when purchasing new weapons systems. Historically, performance, cost, and schedule were the most important criteria in selecting new weapons systems for the Air Force inventory. The R&M 2000 program places reliability and maintainability on an equal level with the other three criteria (Ref 1). How does the Air Force and its contractors develop and build new weapons systems, like the Advanced Tactical Fighter (ATF), that exhibit good R&M qualities without sacrificing performance, cost, or schedule? The Air Force is advocating new technologies for the answer. The Self-Repairing Flight Control System (SRFCS) advanced development program is part of this

answer. The SRFCS program objective is to develop and transition technology that improves reliability, maintainability, and survivability of fighter aircraft flight control systems while simultaneously reducing life cycle cost.

The SRFCS program uses several figures of merit. Mean Flight Time Between Failures (MFTBF) is a measure of the frequency of system maintenance. The MFTBF numbers correspond to type I inherent failures. The mean time to diagnose a fault is an important R&M metric because it represents a significant portion of the time taken to return an aircraft to flight status. Life Cycle Cost (LCC) is also an important metric for evaluating R&M technologies. Improvements in reliability and maintainability have a direct effect on the costs of acquiring new systems, spares, test and support equipment, transportation, and maintenance labor. The effect of R&M technologies on aircraft weight impacts performance. Other metrics used for evaluating R&M technologies such as combat effectiveness, sortie generation, infrastructure survivability, and mobility, are more difficult to measure because they depend on the fidelity of simulations used and assumptions made in combat scenarios.

Two R&M metrics require definition. Statistics on CanNot Duplicates (CND) and ReTest OKs (RETOK) represent inefficiencies in maintenance. A CND is an indicated fault, often stemming from pilot debriefings, that the maintenance personnel cannot reproduce on the ground. For example, the failure may be one that only occurs with high g's, vibration, or temperature. CNDs often lead to maintenance personnel removing operational components and sending them to the intermediate shop or depot. Intermediate shop or depot personnel test the components, find nothing wrong with them (RETOK), and send them back to the flight line. CNDs and RETOKs represent wasted effort, time, money, and reduced readiness.

To understand current R&M problems, SRFCS program engineers examined the Maintenance and Operational Data Access System (MODAS) and the Centralized Data System (CDS) data bases for the flight control systems of F-15C/Ds and F-16As (Ref 2). The flight control systems for F-16s and F-15s consist of all components and subsystems within work unit code 14; actuators, control surfaces, sensors, computers, and miscellaneous

components. The engineers found significant R&M problems. The overall MFTBF for F-16s and F-15s is between one and four hours. The flight control systems of these aircraft have MFTBFs between 25 and 50 hours, which contributes significantly to the low overall MFTBF. When failures occur, the mean time to diagnose is eight manhours. This is due to the complexity of the flight control system, cumbersome volumes of technical orders, insufficient fault indicators, and a shortage of test equipment. These problems and a lack of knowledge of the conditions under which failures occur in flight leads to 31% of F-16A failure records being CNDs and 34% being RETOKS (Ref 2).

The SRFCS program attacks both low component reliability and inefficient maintenance through the development of two technologies, control surface reconfiguration and automated maintenance diagnostics. Reconfiguration uses remaining functional control surfaces (e.g., ailerons, stabilators, canards, rudders, etc.) to automatically substitute for other control surfaces that become impaired. With this new functional redundancy, design engineers can simplify and reduce brute force replication of components upstream of the control surfaces. This leads to significant improvements in MFTBF. Through the application of expert system technology, maintenance diagnostics systems monitor and diagnose flight control system faults in the air and aid maintenance personnel on the ground. The expert diagnostic systems nearly eliminate CNDs and RETOKS and allow maintenance personnel to quickly and efficiently return aircraft to flight status.

Reconfiguration and maintenance diagnostics significantly increase the time between required maintenance, shorten repair time, and reduce acquisition and support costs. The SRFCS program contributes to the Air Force objective of producing high performance aircraft, such as the ATF, that are reliable, maintainable, and affordable.

The program is composed of four tasks designed to satisfy the objective (Fig 1). The Reconfiguration Technology Development for Future Fighters addresses the reliability, survivability, and life cycle cost objectives. The Maintenance Diagnostics tasks addresses the maintainability objective. The Proof of Concept Flight Demonstration and Advanced SRFCS Flight Demonstration tasks support technology transition to new weapon systems. The tasks are discussed in the following paragraphs.

2. RECONFIGURATION TECHNOLOGY DEVELOPMENT FOR FUTURE FIGHTERS

2.1 Introduction

The task objective is the design of a reconfigurable control system for an advanced fighter to yield increased warfighting capability, increased survivability, reduced support requirements, and lower life cycle costs. The increased

capability and critical reconfiguration technologies are demonstrated in a piloted simulation.

To achieve these objectives, the task is composed of three components: Feasibility Demonstration, Control Reconfigurable Combat Aircraft Design Study, and Control Reconfigurable Combat Aircraft Simulation. Each of these components are covered in the following sections.

2.2 Feasibility Demonstration

Loss of control can be prevented by redistributing remaining control authority after actuator and surface damage. Lessons learned from the Vietnam Era show 20% of aircraft losses were due to flight control damage. Loss of hydraulics, actuator damage, and surface damage are responsible for most of the FCS losses.

The simulation is a high fidelity, non-linear, man-in-the-loop, motion based, model of the AFTI/F-16 (Fig 2). The simulation models actuator failure and control surface damage. When damage occurs, a System Impairment Detection and Classification module isolates the damage and an Effector Gain Estimator determines the remaining forces and moment capability of the aircraft (Ref 3). A control mixer module reconfigures the control laws to maintain stability and maximum performance.

The simulation demonstrated that, after severe failures and damage, the reconfigured AFTI/F-16 has decreased departures, increased maneuver performance, reduced tracking error, improved handling qualities, and reduced transients (Ref 4). Specifically, reconfiguration prevented departure for severe single surface failure cases, such as floating stabilator, and prevented departure for the majority of severe dual surface failure cases. Given further development and refinement of the reconfiguration algorithms, 70% of the severe failure departure cases could have been prevented. These refinements, such as a pilot alert module, saturation handling, and command limiting, are covered under the Control Reconfigurable Combat Aircraft Simulation.

Reconfiguration is a valid technique for improving the survivability of fighter aircraft. In addition, the increased fault tolerance that reconfiguration yields permits a reduction in flight control system hardware redundancy. The Control Reconfigurable Combat Aircraft Design Study explores the hardware simplification potential for an advanced aircraft.

2.3 Control Reconfigurable Combat Aircraft Design Study

2.3.1 Introduction

The design study objective is to determine the impact of surface reconfiguration on Advanced Tactical Fighter class aircraft. The specific goals of this study are:

- 360 hr MTBF (type 1) for FCS
- 30% reduction in acquisition and support costs
- less than 1% attrition due to FCS

The basic approach exploits the inherent redundancy of the control structure of advanced fighter aircraft. These aircraft have multipurpose control effectors that, when properly designed, can compensate for one another. The resulting robust control structure is augmented with an onboard reconfiguration algorithm that compensates for crosscoupling. Use of simplex actuators (connected to one hydraulics system versus two) yield the largest improvement in MTBF. To allow simplex actuators, the hydraulic system must be designed accordingly. Finally, the basic architecture can be streamlined due to the inherent fault tolerance.

The study has made considerable progress toward the goals. Over 200 hrs MTBF is achieved by simplification. Any further increases requires a detailed follow-up of failures. The simplifications resulted in a 25% decrease in FCS acquisition costs. The attrition rate goal is surpassed and there is a 4-5% increase in targets killed. The following paragraphs discuss the changes to the system.

2.3.2 Aircraft Control Structure

The objective is to desensitize the aircraft performance to loss of any one control surface in the three rotational and lift axes. This is done without adding any further surfaces and can result in a reduction of surfaces. The elimination of critical surfaces reduces the need for upstream redundancy to ensure the surface is operational at all times.

Grumman Aerospace Corp is performing the study based on the Research Fighter Configuration (RFC). The RFC is a 35k pound high performance air superiority fighter designed for supersonic cruise. Eight vectoring actuators are charged to the FCS and severely penalize the MTBF. Little gain can be made in MTBF with them, therefore alternatives were investigated for their removal.

Flaps and canards supply sufficient pitch control at low dynamic pressure such that pitch vectoring is not required. The canards have a dihedral of 30 degrees which yield sufficient yaw control at low dynamic pressure such that yaw vectoring is not needed. The dihedral canards supply the landing yaw control of yaw vectoring without the complexity.

The Control Reconfigurable Combat Aircraft (CRCA) is very robust and is landable with any one, two, or three surface failures except both canards and rudder (Fig 3). The CRCA has no critical surfaces and does not need complex redundant actuators. The CRCA can maintain a higher level of performance after failures than the RFC with fewer surfaces. The CRCA meets all the performance specifications of the RFC with no structural or aerodynamic penalties. There is a

net saving in weight. The robust control structure is exploited in the actuator design.

2.3.3 Actuation

The objective is to simplify the actuator subsystem. The actuators, as a group, have the lowest MTBF and highest cost of FCS components. Actuators are complex because of the critical surfaces they drive.

The greatest gains stem from substituting duplex actuators with simplex. The actuator MTBF increases from 2000 hrs to nearly 6000 hrs. Further simplifications are made using damped bypass as the failure mode instead of a mechanical lock. Damped bypass is initiated when hydraulic or electrical power is lost.

The key to simplex actuators, however, is the hydraulic system. For the purposes of this study, the aircraft retains a central hydraulic system of approximately 3000 psi. Other designs, such as Electro Hydro-static Actuators, may obviate a central hydraulic system, but there is technical risk for a 1989 technology availability date. As a worst case, the final CRCA decision will have no more than three dual-tandem actuators out of nine. The actuators represent the bulk of the acquisition cost savings.

2.3.4 Hydraulics

The objective is to design a hydraulic system with the desired performance using simplex actuators. The challenge in using simplex actuators is in not penalizing the hydraulic system. There can be no net gain if the hydraulic system becomes more complex.

The hydraulic systems of modern fighters were analyzed for their capabilities under various failures. No aircraft today has all the capabilities exhibited by a composite of the various hydraulic systems. The majority of the systems have full capability after one and sometimes two piece-part failures. Any further failure would be catastrophic. This full capability after failure results in significant redundancy and complexity. The most onerous capability of current aircraft is full performance with complete loss of one system. This normally dictates a dual-tandem actuator approach. However, this design is vulnerable because the hydraulic lines of two systems are in very close proximity at the actuators. Damage to them can result in loss of two systems and loss of the aircraft. The SRFC approach is a gradual degradation in performance after failures.

There are numerous hydraulic system designs for the CRCA, all supporting simplex actuators to a degree (Fig 4). CRCA-3 design has a Probability of Loss of Control (PLOC) that is better than many current hydraulic systems. However, the abort rate may be higher if stringent criteria are applied. As a rule, flight is aborted for any hydraulic problem. If the same criterion is applied to this system, the abort rate would be the same, but the aborts would more

often involve degraded performance. The CRCA control structure minimizes this performance degradation. The hydraulic and actuator simplification presents other opportunities for simplification in the FCS architecture.

2.3.5 Architecture

The objective is to minimize hardware duplication. Most of the CRCA architecture benefits are achieved from dual tetrads and triplex computers. The sensors are shared with the navigation system. The computers have extensive inline monitoring and no backup that would increase the probability of degraded performance.

Examination of baseline computer unreliability reveals that nearly half of the failures are due to actuator Input/Output drivers. In CRCA each computer drives 2/3 of the actuators, eliminating 1/3 of the drivers. The actuators have dual command inputs and dual ram position outputs. However, the system would lose 1/3 of the actuators after a dual computer failure. This event has a low probability, but the aircraft would remain flyable and landable.

These simplifications result in over 700 hr MTBF for the architecture composed of sensors and computers. There is a net reduction in weight, power, size, and cost.

2.3.6 Summary

The CRCA design increased MTBF from 85 to over 200 hrs (Ref 5). Further increases are achievable by concentrating on actuator failure modes such as shorts, corrosion, and leaks. Miscellaneous FCS components would require similar attention to achieve a 360 hr MTBF. The SRFCFS program has not concentrated on these failure modes.

The PLOC achieved in the study is consistent with contemporary fighters. Further work should be done on the hydraulic system to assure that PLOC and the abort rate are acceptable and there are no other dominant failure modes. Allied with PLOC is the vulnerability goal. The design has gone beyond the desired 1% attrition rate to .01% due to the improved fault and damage tolerant control structure. Because there are no system rewards for the additional survivability, more work should be done to trade in the excess for further improved MTBF or cost.

Cost savings are contingent on the assumptions made. If the reduced performance associated with removal of thrust vectoring is acceptable, then over \$2B can be saved for the fleet (LCC). If thrust vectoring must remain on the aircraft for requirements other than Short TakeOff and Landing (STOL), \$200K can still be saved per aircraft in acquisition costs. There is a 200 lb savings in weight as well, which, with appropriate multiplicative factors, can translate into \$1M LCC savings per aircraft.

As part of the design study, Grumman is developing a handbook for the design and evaluation of fault tolerant reconfigurable architectures. Primary emphasis is impact on Mil-F-8785 and 9490D. Other areas concentrated on are flexibility effects, structural damage/aero effects, digital architectures, and the effects of configuration constraints on reconfiguration algorithms.

2.4 Control Reconfigurable Combat Aircraft Simulation

2.4.1 Introduction

The CRCA simulation demonstrates, through piloted simulation, that: ATF type performance capabilities are met, distributed control power and reconfiguration compensate for reduced hardware redundancy, and reconfiguration algorithms are practical and implementable.

The simulation is hosted on the Large Amplitude Multi mode Aerospace Research Simulator (LAMARS) at Wright-Patterson Air Force Base. The CRCA aircraft simulation, developed under the design study, can model actuator and control surface failures. The Flight Control Computer (FCC) from the design study is emulated and contains the control laws, Failure Detection and Isolation (FDI), Pseudo-Surface Resolver (PSR), and the Positive Pilot Alert (PPA). The piloted tests concentrate on four flight conditions which are representative of the flight profile.

Preliminary results show the CRCA performance is not sensitive to trailing edge flap failures. Canard failures have the biggest impact on aerodynamics. Hydraulic failures, however, are the most serious as they impact several surfaces simultaneously. The following sections discuss the aircraft model, FCC software, PPA, and test scenarios.

2.4.2 Aircraft Model

The CRCA model (Fig 5) accurately represents failure and damage effects over a range of maneuvers and flight conditions. The aerodynamic model is valid over the subsonic envelope, but the control algorithms are designed for Air Combat Maneuvering (ACM) entry, ACM exit, Terrain Following/Terrain Avoidance (TF/TA), and STOL.

Flexibility effects on control effectiveness at high dynamic pressure are included. Structural mode higher order dynamic effects such as Flexibility, sensor noise, sensor placement, and notch filtering are accounted for in the control system gains. Damage effects are modeled as an equivalent percent loss in control effectiveness.

Actuator failure modes include locked, runaway, and floating. When the actuator is no longer operative it can be commanded into damped bypass where the surface floats, but is heavily

damped. The model data base is adequate, but more work should be done on canard damage effects. Analytical Methods Incorporated constructed a panel model of the CRCA which supplements the wind tunnel testing.

2.4.3 Flight Control Computer

The FCC emulation (Fig 6) is representative of an implementation of the reconfiguration and FDI algorithms. Lear Astronics Corp modified the baseline control laws to be more robust to surface failures (Ref 6). Additional refinements were added such as command limiting and scheduling that were needed for a piloted simulation.

Charles River Analytics developed both local and global FDI algorithms. The reconfiguration logic uses this information to restructure the control gains. Local FDI isolates actuator locked, runaway, and floating failures (Ref 7). Global FDI isolates surface damage and estimates the remaining control effectiveness. The global FDI contains a simple aircraft model. The residuals are operated on by a bank of detectors, one for each surface. Each detector tries to fit all the error in the residuals to its failure hypothesis. Likelihood ratio filters, in turn, determine how well the data fit the hypotheses. To minimize false alarms, the filters include distinguishability criteria to ensure the failure signature is unique. An m-ary test selects the highest likelihood hypothesis. The filters continuously calculate an estimate of control effectiveness in parallel with the isolation process.

The Pseudo-Surface Resolver (PSR), developed by Lear, reallocates control power based on inputs from local and global FDI. The PSR is a modified pseudo-inverse that minimizes changes in control deflections after failure to maintain forces and moments. A pseudo-inverse, however, often results in large gains that tend to drive the surfaces into saturation. The PSR adds a series of constraints to the pseudo-inverse that prevents saturation, minimizes crosscoupling, and yields lower gains that change more smoothly. The PSR recovers maximum performance consistent with stability and available control power.

2.4.4 Positive Pilot Alert

The FCC processor also contains the PPA module. This module informs the pilot of system status for mission decisions. The need for this module was identified from the feasibility study where the pilot often departed the aircraft because he was not aware of any control restrictions.

Following failures the PPA module answers the pilot's questions of: what happened, what do I do, what can I do, and where do I go. The PPA module is table driven using flags from the FDI as an index. The tables produce maneuvering, envelope, and mission restrictions as a function of failures. Any failures that require immediate action are placed on the Head Up Display (HUD).

More detailed, less immediate information is available on the Multi-Functional Display (MFD). There are three MFD displays: Flight Status, FCS Status, and Emergency Procedures. They are selectable by the pilot as the situation requires. The PPA aids the pilot in not pushing the impaired aircraft beyond its new limits.

2.4.5 Simulation Scenario

The piloted tests provide a realistic test of the CRCA and its reconfigurable control laws. The piloted simulation, supported by Century Computing, uses the LAMARS motion base. The simulation has an F-15 cockpit, F-16 sidestick, F-16 center console, and a F-18 wide field of view HUD. A detailed set of handling qualities tests are run at the four flight conditions both without and with failures. A team of operational pilots fly three scenarios and provide comments on performance. The three scenarios are STOL, TF/TA by steering to waypoints, and tracking a target from ACM entry to exit. The failures and damage are inserted at random times. These tests provide a realistic evaluation of the reconfiguration algorithms.

3. Maintenance Diagnostics

The objective of the maintenance diagnostics systems developed under the SRFCS program is to accurately isolate failures to a repairable unit. The SRFCS program is developing the maintenance diagnostics systems through two contracted efforts. One is a feasibility design study and demonstration performed by the General Electric Company, the other is an advanced design study and demonstration performed by Honeywell, Incorporated. Honeywell will develop design criteria for ground and airborne maintenance diagnostics systems which aid the technology transition to the ATF.

3.1 Flight Control Ground Diagnostics

The Government contracted the General Electric Company to demonstrate the feasibility and applicability of a ground based maintenance diagnostics system that helps maintenance technicians efficiently isolate and repair flight control system faults (Ref 3). General Electric, using artificial intelligence technology, developed the General Electric Maintenance System (GEMS) that runs on a portable, IBM personal computer. The demonstration system covers fourteen F-15 FCS fault codes (Fig 7).

GEMS is a rule based expert system consisting of a knowledge base, an inference engine, and a user interface. The knowledge base contains information about the system, such as component descriptions, diagrams, input/output relationships, fault trees, and test repair procedures. The inference engine contains the reasoning that an expert (e.g. the system designer or an experienced maintenance technician) would use in choosing and performing tests, analyzing results, and isolating faults. The GEMS inference engine is

based on If-And-Only-If rules. The user interface allows flight line maintenance technicians to quickly and easily interact with the maintenance diagnostics system. GEMS is more than automated technical orders. It includes the expertise of flight control system design engineers and experienced aircraft maintenance technicians to provide an inexperienced technician with the quickest and easiest isolation tests. The technician answers questions based on the outcome of the tests and the system suggests more testing if needed. GEMS also provides detailed repair instructions including video disk help facilities (Ref 3).

3.2 Flight Control Maintenance Diagnostics Systems

The Systems and Research Center of Honeywell, Incorporated, is performing the Flight Control Maintenance Diagnostic System (FCMDS) effort which is an advanced design of both ground and airborne maintenance diagnostics systems. The objective of the Honeywell contract is to develop and demonstrate maintenance diagnostics systems that accurately isolate flight control system faults both in the air and on the ground. The goal of the ground based system design is to demonstrate a useful expert maintenance diagnostics system that reduces the mean time to diagnose a failure. The goal of the airborne system study is to show that CNDs and RETOKs can be nearly eliminated by embedding a maintenance diagnostics system within the flight control system that isolates faults as they occur.

Honeywell's approach to a ground based system design is similar to GEMS, consisting of a knowledge base, inference engine, and user interface. However, the Honeywell design uses object oriented programming rather than rules. In object oriented programming, knowledge about the system is organized into frames which represent components of the flight control system. A frame contains attributes, which describe the component, and methods, which are LISP functions or operators. The inference engine, therefore, is embedded within the knowledge base through use of the methods. Like GEMS, FCMDS has a user friendly interface to the maintenance technicians. FCMDS aids the technicians through all stages of maintenance including pilot debriefing, setting up the aircraft for maintenance, verifying the fault, isolating the fault, repairing the problem, and restoring the aircraft to flight status. FCMDS also records information about the faults for a historical data base. To date, the ground FCMDS covers the pitch axis of the F-16A flight control system with work continuing toward complete coverage (Fig 8).

The embedded diagnostics design study started recently. The embedded system receives information from electronic buses, built in test signals, voting planes, the FDI algorithm, Time-Stress Management Devices, and any other sensor information already available on the aircraft (Fig 8). The embedded diagnostics constantly monitors the flight control system and records information over

a moving window of time. When a failure occurs, the diagnostics system records the state of the aircraft (e.g., temperature, vibration, g loading, etc.) just before the fault. The system then diagnoses the problem in the air. The results of the diagnosis is stored for use by ground technicians.

Honeywell is developing design criteria for maintenance diagnostics systems. The criteria study considers the impact on maintenance diagnostics system design of proposed technical advances for future fighter aircraft, such as increased usage of digital electronics, distributed systems, and vehicle management systems. The design criteria report is oriented to the ATF program office and contractors.

4. Proof of Concept Flight Demonstration

The primary SRFCs goal is the transition of reconfiguration and maintenance diagnostics technology to the ATF. A major constraint is the nearness of the ATF technology availability date, currently November, 1989. The previously discussed design criteria constitutes a large step in the transition process, however, a flight demonstration on a high performance aircraft is necessary to complete the transition. Therefore, the Air Force let a contract through NASA to McDonnell Douglas Aircraft Corporation to flight demonstrate the SRFCs technologies on NASA's Highly Integrated Digital Electronic Control (HIDEC) F-15 aircraft in time for the technology availability date.

The proof of concept demonstration has limited scope but gives credibility to the reconfiguration and maintenance diagnostics technologies. The flight condition is limited to the region around 0.7 Mach, 20,000 feet. The SRFCs algorithms are hosted on a Rolm Hawk and can be switched out of the primary flight control system (Fig 9). The HIDEC aircraft is modified to allow computer control of the ailerons. Impairments to single horizontal tail stabilator is emulated. Failure modes include control surface floating and locking. Reconfiguration after the emulated failure indicates fault tolerance to impairments upstream of the horizontal tail surface. Reduced aircraft vulnerability is demonstrated by reconfiguring for emulated missing surface area of the horizontal stabilator. A positive pilot alert system informs the pilot of the emulated failures on the head up display.

The onboard maintenance diagnostics system will be developed and flown in two phases. The first phase is a piggy back flight test of the inference engine. The objective is to prove the system can isolate to an emulated angle of attack probe failure. Signals from the two probes are sent to the Rolm Hawk computer where an artificial lag, added to one of the probe signals, emulates a sticking angle of attack probe. This failure causes the control augmentation system to drop offline, but maintenance personnel cannot duplicate the failure on the ground, leading to a

CND. The onboard diagnostics system, however, interrogates other FCS signals and monitors, inferences on the information, and isolates to the faulty probe in flight. The second phase expands the system to cover other FCS component failures, including actuator failure modes where information from the reconfiguration algorithms helps isolate the fault. Although not a full system implementation, the Proof of Concept Demonstration is sufficient for technology transition to the ATF.

5. Advanced SRFCFS Flight Demonstration

The Advanced SRFCFS (ASRFCS) flight demonstration goal is the transition of SRFCFS technologies to aircraft systems beyond initial ATF production, such as F-15 or F-16 block modifications, future ATF block modifications, and close air support vehicles. The scope of the ASRFCS demonstration is greatly expanded from the proof of concept demonstration. The demo embeds reconfiguration, FDI, positive pilot alert, and maintenance diagnostics algorithms in the primary flight control system. The SRFCFS algorithms cover the entire flight control system and reconfigure for single or multiple failures of control surfaces. The emulated control surface impairments demonstrate improved fault tolerance through reconfiguration and reduced aircraft vulnerability. The maintenance diagnostics system covers all the flight control system and interfaces with the other SRFCFS algorithms. The ASRFCS demonstration program includes: a detailed examination of aeroservoelastic effects and structural loading following reconfiguration; unconventional reconfiguration techniques, such as use of speedbrakes; and advanced flight control system architectures and components.

As stated previously, significant R&M and cost benefits are gained from use of simplex versus duplex actuators. Advanced actuators, such as electro hydrostatic and electro mechanical actuators, may replace contemporary hydraulic actuators. The major benefit of self contained actuators is elimination of centralized hydraulic systems leading to greatly reduced vulnerability and improved R&M. The concept of control surface reconfiguration can simplify advanced actuators e.g., allow use of single pump/motors on primary control surfaces versus dual. Current plans are to fly one or more simplex electro hydrostatic actuators on the ASRFCS flight test and demonstrate that reconfiguration handles the failure modes of these actuators.

In parallel with the ASRFCS demonstration is a field demonstration of a ground maintenance diagnostics system. Several prototype ground diagnostics units will be demonstrated and tested on an F-16 flight line over a period of six months.

6. Conclusion

The Self-Repairing Flight Control System program offers two technologies, control surface

reconfiguration and expert maintenance diagnostics, to current and future Air Force fighter aircraft. These technologies improve reliability, maintainability, and survivability while reducing acquisition and operating costs. The SRFCFS program is transitioning these technologies to the ATF and other aircraft.

7. References

1. USAF R&M 2000 Process, Headquarters, United States Air Force Office of the Special Assistant for R&M, Washington, D.C., October 1987.
2. Flight Control Maintenance Diagnostic System (FCMDS), R&D Evaluation Report, Technology Assessment (CDRL #7), Contract F33615-85-C-3613, Honeywell Inc, Systems and Research Center.
3. Self-Repairing Digital Flight Control System Study, Final Report, January 1988, General Electric Company, Aircraft Control Systems Department.
4. USAF AFTI/F-16 Self-Repairing Flight Control System Simulation NAECON 1987, Dayton, Ohio.
5. Control Reconfigurable Combat Aircraft Development Phase I - R&D Design Evaluation, AFWAL-TR-3011, May 1987, Grumman Aerospace Corporation.
6. Reconfiguration Strategies for Aircraft with Flight Control Systems Subjected to Actuator Failure/Surface Damage, AFWAL-TR-86-3110, March 1987, Lear Siegler, Inc.
7. A Hierarchical Reconfiguration Strategy for Aircraft Subjected to Actuator Failure/Surface Damage, AFWAL-TR-3024, May 1987, Charles River Analytics.
8. Flight Control Maintenance Diagnostic System (FCMDS), Laboratory Demonstration System Documentation, Honeywell, Inc., July 1987.

Fig 1 SRFCFS Program Schedule

SUBSYSTEM FUNCTION:
SIDC - DETERMINES SURFACE IMPAIRED AND TYPE OF IMPAIRMENT
EGE! - ESTIMATES EXTENT OF IMPAIRMENT (FOR PARTIALLY MISSING SURFACE)
MIXER - REDISTRIBUTES REMAINING EFFECTIVENESS TO OVERCOME IMPAIRMENT

Fig 2 Reconfigurable AFTI/F-16 Simulation

MISSION STATE	NUMBER OF SURFACE FAILURES					
	BASELINE			RECONFIGURABLE		
	ROLL	PITCH	YAW	ROLL	PITCH	YAW
SEEK PRIMARY TARGET	0	0	0 TO 1	0 TO 1	0 TO 1	0
SEEK SECONDARY TARGET	1 TO 2	NC	NC	2	2	1
ABORT MISSION	3	1	2	3	3	2
CAVASTROPHIC	4	2	3	4	4	3
MINIMUM OF AVAILABLE SURFACES ALOFT AKES	6	4	3	6	8	3

↓ GRACEFUL DEGRADATION

Fig 3 CRCA Control Structure Fault Tolerant

CONFIGURATION	SYSTEMS	PUMPS	BACKUP POWER	SWITCH VALVES	SIMPLEX ACT	DUAL TANDEM	XPRR PUMPS	BLS	PLOC
CRCA-1	3	3	1	2	4	5	2	2	0.41 E-10
CRCA-2	3	4	1	2	9	-	-	-	0.10 E-7
BASELINE	3	3	1	2	6	11	2	2	0.12 E-6
CRCA-3	2	2	1	-	9	-	2	2	0.15 E-6
F-16	2	2	1	-	-	7	-	-	0.70 E-6

Fig 4 CRCA Hydraulic System Options

Fig 5 Control Reconfigurable Combat Aircraft

Fig 9 Proof of Concept Flight Demonstration Architecture

Fig 6 CRCA Emulated Flight Control Computer

F-15 DEMONSTRATION

- ADA CHANNEL FAILURE
- 1 FAULT CODE ≈ 50 PROO RULES ('83)
- SYSTEM REDESIGNED FOR IFF DEDUCTIVE RULE LOGIC
- SYSTEM AUTO MATICALLY ISOLATES BELOW THE LRU LEVEL (EE WIRES/CONNECTORS)
- DEMONSTRATION CAPABILITY (1985) INCLUDES 16 FAULT CODES AT 2 M BYTES
- TOTAL F-15 FCS SIZED TO LESS THAN 20 M BYTES AND RUNS ON A PC

Fig 7 F-15 Flight Control Ground Diagnostics

Fig 8 Embedded Flight Control Maintenance Diagnostics System

